

Interfaces for Improvising with a Jazz Melody Generation System

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Abstract

Computational models of melody can provide expert knowledge to novices, allowing for access to musical creativity without the need for extensive formal training. This thesis attempts to demonstrate that melody creation and composition can be computationally modelled, and documents the development of an interactive model of jazz melody generation intended to be used in a live performance context. By incorporating a melody generation system, developed using variable order Markov chains, which takes into account the harmonic context at each moment, relevant and stylistically consistent note suggestions are delivered to a user in real time. Focussing on jazz melodies specifically, two prospective interfaces were developed that allow a performer interact and direct the melody generation in collaboration with the system, allowing for live performance. Real world instrument metaphors were eschewed in favour of novel interfaces that deal with the affordances of readily available technology, such as touch screen devices. Both computational and human evaluation of the melodic output of the system are proposed, along with user testing in order to review both the musical and performance aspects of the system.

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1 Introduction

Creativity has always been the aspect of music that has impressed me the most, with a musicians' individual ability to express themselves in a completely different manner to anyone else an infinite source of surprise and interest to me. Developments in the field of algorithmic composition and the means to involve users in the process of music creation through the means of technology presents the opportunity to democratise music creation, and to allow anyone to access their own musical creativity, regardless of whether their musical training is formal, informal or completely non-existent. I'd like to believe that everybody has the ability to be creative, so to remove a complex and intimidating barrier to musical creativity for many people, and replace it with a computational model, would allow a new group of creative people the ability to make music, which would hopefully end with more surprising and novel music to enjoy. In addition to this, the opportunity to be the designer of the system which helps to unlock the creativity in all of these people presents the chance to collaborate musically with and influence the musical output of so many more people than would be possible is an exciting prospect.

Since smartphones and tablets have become commonplace in homes in western countries, touch screens have become ubiquitous in the developed world, and by placing a device with a large touch surface and accelerometer and gyroscope sensors into the pocket of a large number of people, an opportunity exists to present a new interaction method. However, the majority of musical performance and synthesis applications currently available for such devices consist of touch screen metaphors for existing interaction paradigms, such as a musical keyboard or electronic drum machine¹. While these applications make use of these devices' portability and powerful computing power for their size, they don't take advantage of the new means of interaction afforded by the touch screens of the devices, and they are also forced to compromise the interaction experience from which the original metaphors came from. For example, a number of applications use a touch screen version of a musical keyboard^{2 3}, but without the physical feedback that a user receives from pressing a physical key, which of course lacks the physical feedback one would receive when pressing a physical key. Alongside this, such applications often cram an octave or two of keys into the space usually afforded to 4 or 5 keys of a physical keyboard, and the combination of these two compromises mean that it is almost impossible to match the accuracy that is possible on a physical keyboard on the touch screen. At the other extreme, other applications for music creation that explore alternative interaction paradigms are often highly constrained, and end up restricting a user to purely realising a pre-meditated piece of music, rather than composing themselves^{4 5}.

¹ KORG INC., "KORG iELECTRIBE for iPad," 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/korg-ielectribe-for-ipad/id363714043?mt=8>.

² Apple Inc., "GarageBand," 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/garageband/id408709785?mt=8>.

³ Z. Yang, "PianoTM HD," 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/piano-hd/id526625728?mt=8>.

⁴ Opal Limited, "Bloom," 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/bloom/id292792586?mt=8>.

⁵ Radiohead, "Polyfauna," 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/polyfauna/id793263070?mt=8>.

Despite the large potential of the interaction methods, the touch screen is yet to be widely accepted as a performance instrument, aside from for DJ applications. Following on from these observations, it seems there is an opportunity to develop a performance solution for touch screens by either reconsidering the keyboard metaphor for a touch screen device, and adapting it to better suit the strengths and weaknesses of the device; or to explore a completely new interaction paradigm which makes full use of the capabilities of a touch screen device. As well as new interaction methods that this would provide, a widely-accepted touch screen instrument could also help to democratise musical performance, as it could present a highly accessible instrument, given the availability of such devices.

If both of these problems are considered together, there appears an opportunity to expand the possibilities of touch screen devices, and introduce a new interface in order to better utilise the affordances of touch screen devices while concurrently producing a performance instrument that is engaging and worthwhile for both the musically trained and musical novices. By combining the fields of algorithmic composition with musical interface design, a novel performance instrument could be designed that provides a contribution that deals with the problems discussed above.

1.1 Aims

The primary aims of this project are:

1. To create a melody generation system and an interface to interact with it
2. Implement a novel interface that makes better use of touch screens' capabilities

Following on from this, the resulting instrument should be viable as a performance instrument, more specifically be able to be used as an improvisational tool in a live performance context. In addition to this, it should be engaging for both trained and untrained musicians. Consequently, in order to make the instrument practical for live performance situations, it should be constrained to a specific style or genre in order to be able to provide a sufficient level of expert knowledge to the user. To this end, jazz music has been chosen for the purposes of this project, not only because jazz music has a tradition of improvisation and live performance ingrained in its tradition, but also because there is a significant amount of literature and materials available for jazz music.

2 State of the Art

Considering this project represents the combination of a number of existing fields of research, the state of the art will be split into sections relating to these fields. First, models relating to the cognitive theory of melody will be discussed, in order to provide a thorough background on melody from a cognitive standpoint. Secondly, methods for and applications of automatic composition and melody generation will be considered, followed by a review of research surrounding the development of interfaces for musical interaction. Following this, these contributions to the state of the art will be considered together, and their impact on this research will be discussed.

2.1 Cognitive Theory of Melody

In order to fully understand the underlying aspects of the creation and perception of melodies, it's important to consider the cognitive processes that occur during the creative process. It has been argued that research based on audio and music should always consider cognitive processes, as the cognitive perception of sound and music form the definition of music, seeing as the perception of sound is. Furthermore, it has also been presented that biological systems can provide suitable inspiration for solving musical problems, as computational models for music and audio are often interpretations of biological systems [1].

The most widely accepted and comprehensive theory of melody perception and cognition is Narmour's Implication-Realization (IR) model [2], which proposes a rule based model to understand the cognitive aspects of melody expectation. The model states that the implication of intervals is derived from two processes utilising learned information as well as pre-existing mechanisms, which Narmour describes as top-down and bottom-up processes respectively. By hypothesising that these processes have a direct relationship with our expectation of intervallic motion, he was able to create a rule based model to infer universal and stylistically relevant expectations of melody continuation. More latterly, Schellenberg has provided a rigorous examination of the IR model, first offering a novel evaluation method of Narmour's original principles by developing an experiment to measure listeners' responses to melodic fragments [3], thus measuring the predictive accuracy of the model. By making the model measurable and being able to attribute numerical results to the output, Schellenberg was able to make improvements to the IR model by simplifying Narmour's original rules while maintaining similar prediction accuracy [4].

Pearce & Wiggins also build on Schellenberg's empirical testing of the IR model [5] and propose an amendment to the original model by inducing statistical regularities in order to improve the prediction accuracy of the model for wider ranges of musical experience in test subjects. They proffer that the previously accepted model is too inflexible to differing levels of musical experience, and by exploring a statistical model of surface level musical events, they imply a model that is more accurate for both musically experienced and novice users. They also demonstrate that this amendment provides better empirical results than Schellenberg's simplified model. Both Schellenberg's and Pierce & Wiggins' research demonstrates that Narmour's model is able to consistently describe and predict melody expectation in empirical tests, and additionally that the

original IR model can be improved by both simplification as well as augmentation. By providing an empirical framework for evaluating the IR model, this research has opened up the field to be improved by future research, and allowing an iterable and progressive version of the IR model to be developed.

Moving further towards compositional aspects and applications of the IR model, Anta & Martinez explored the applications to compositional tasks of the IR model [6]. By providing empirical analysis of melody continuations provided by 20 students of music composition, they were able to demonstrate that Schellenberg's revised model was able to accurately describe the processes involved in melody expectancy, however they do highlight specific areas where the model fails to accurately predict intervals, particularly concerning small intervals.

Smith & Holland have demonstrated that the IR model and Narmour's theory can be applied to a computational model of melody generation [7]. By applying a set of criteria derived from the IR model to prospective notes, they determined that the IR model could be used as a generative model for composition. They propose the tool as an educational tool for composers, primarily in an offline capacity. Pachet is another who has explored the role of constraints in melody generation [8], with his work studying how constraints can improve the interactability of a system based on Markovian sequences, following on from his applications of Markovian processes in his interactive melody continuator, The Continuator [9]. He supposes that the addition of control specifications as constraints allow the system to be "naturally steerable", and allows the application of constraint based melody generation in a real-time situation.

Aside from Narmour's IR model, there are a number of other models that aspire to understand and predict the cognitive functions involved in melody perception. Pearce [10] has proposed a theory of melodic expectancy based on the induction of statistical regularities in melodic content to provide insight and a means of evaluation into the processes involved in melodic perception and composition. By connecting perception and composition, Pearce is able to model melodic composition strategies in a way that deals with the discrepancy between mathematical and music theory based models of melodic perception. In addition to this, Pearce's model is also able to model melodic expectation, similarly to Narmour's model at both the computational and perceptual level.

2.1.1 Applications of Melody Expectancy to Jazz

There are a number of examples of direct applications of Narmour's IR model to Jazz music, as well as specific examples of Jazz generation, with Grachten and Arcos' use of the IR model as a means of measuring melodic similarity a notable example [11]. By observing the edit-distances between the aspects of analysis that comprise the IR model, they are able to provide a distance measurement between two melodies that balances abstract and concrete aspects of melody and melody measurement. Their analysis material comprises of 40 Real Book jazz compositions, split into 124 phrases from the melodies contained within the pieces. They concluded that more abstract representations of melody differentiated better between melodies than explicit, note-representation measures. They determined that while the IR represented a good compromise between abstract and explicit representations of the melody, and represented a step forward in

melodic similarity measurement, they recognised that further work was needed to determine the results across differing musical styles.

In their jazz improvisation system, Harris and Fitch applied Narmour's model to create a computational fitness function [12], which evaluated jazz melodies based on criteria determined using the analyses of the IR model. While acknowledging that a computational evaluation of jazz melodies is problematic, they offer that the IR model is highly suitable for dealing with improvisational melody, given that the model can provide a value for overall expectancy, which can be used as a relatively objective measure of melodic success. However, their melodic evaluation is completely abstract, and does not compare results against any baseline values, meaning it's difficult to discern whether their results are replicable, but represents a promising melodic evaluation method using Narmour's model.

Focussing on jazz in particular, Hansen, Vuust & Pearce explored the relationship between particular stylistic expertise on melody perception [13]. Through measuring the responses of classical musicians, jazz musicians and non-musicians to rendered jazz solos, they were able to determine whether stylistic knowledge had an effect on a listeners' expectation of melodic continuation. They attempted to measure the difference between stylistic-specific and genre-agnostic musical knowledge through statistical comparison, which determined that both musical and jazz specific knowledge had an effect on the participants' expectancies of melody continuations. This is significant not only in demonstrating a difference between musicians and non-musicians, but also that it demonstrates that there is further difference between musicians of differing stylistic expertise.

2.2 Melody Generation

2.2.1 Definition of terms

There are a number of terms to describe the automatic generation of musical content, including, but not limited to, algorithmic composition, generative music and computer music. It's important to clarify and understand the subtle differences between the terms, and define the aims and ambitions of this project, as well as where melody generation and suggestion fit in. Looking at computer based art in general, Boden [14] proposes the term "generative art" to define works that are, at least in part, produced by a computer, and the more specific "computer generated art" to describe works in which a computer is left to generate a whole piece of art. Both Boden and Galanter's [15] definitions of generative art are inclusive of works that are generated by processes that may not be computerised, such as procedural art like Mozart's *Musikalisches Würfelspiel* (musical dice game), Steve Reich's "It's Gonna Rain" and Terry Riley's "In C", which all outsource some part of the creation to a process or machine.

Generative music is another term that has been widely used, and is often attributed to Brian Eno [16], who defined generative music in a similar way to procedural music, by defining it as *[machines and systems that] "make music with materials and processes I specified, but in combinations and interactions that I did not."* The first appearance of Eno's Generative Music

came in his 1996 *Generative Music 1*⁶ [17], which comprised of generative pieces in the form of software on floppy disk that generated different versions of 12 pieces every time it ran. However, others [18] suggest that “generative music” was a term designed purely as a marketing “rebranding” of more traditional terms such as (real time) algorithmic composition. Algorithmic composition broadly follows a similar definition, and is similarly described as music that is comprised of elements that have generated from a set of rules [19], and similar to Boden’s definition of generative art, is not tied to the concept of computer generated music. Most definitions describe some sort of non-deterministic music that can be better interpreted as composition design rather than the kind of deterministic authorship that is expected from more traditional forms of composition.

Another widely used term is Interactive Music, which has ambiguity due to two broadly accepted definitions. Interactive Music is often used to describe music that changes depending on the actions of the listener, often actions which are unrelated to the music or composition process (also known as dynamic music or adaptive music) [20]. However, Interactive Music could equally describe the output from an interactive system, such as Pachet’s Continuator [9]. The commonality between both of these differing definitions have is that they both concern the generation of music in real time in relation to some kind of input from a listener or performer. Robert Rowe’s research [21] attempts to help define the term Interactive in the musical domain by suggesting a classification for interactive music systems. He proposes to differentiate systems through three dimensions; whether the system is based around a score or a performance paradigm, how the system responds to user inputs, and how expressive the system allows the user. According to Rowe’s classification, the current research should be defined as a performance-based generative instrument, as a sub category of interactive music systems.

Another perspective on interactivity in music automation is that of expert agents, that are able to convey expert information in real time in order to aid the composition and performance of music. Expert agents have been utilised [22] in an EDM specific environment to provide stylistically relevant suggestions in terms of rhythmic patterns, bass lines, chord sequences and synthesis. As this information is built from analysis of EDM tracks, they are able to deliver relevant and consistent information to the user in real time in such a way that augments their ability to compose and perform EDM.

While it has been demonstrated that there are a number of terms describing the automatic generation of musical content, it appears that these can be broadly categorised into two groupings; offline and interactive systems. Offline systems are those that involve generation that happens before the realisation of the music sonically – these include Eno’s *Generative Music 1*, which only renders music after the composition has been generated by the system – and while they may allow for prior parameter tuning by a user, ultimately the user has no role in realising the music, as at the time it is rendered, it has been completely determined by the system. Interactive systems, on the other hand, which include the Continuator, involve input from the user, be it continuous or sporadic, during the generation and realisation phase, which are simultaneous in practice. This differentiates it from an offline system in the sense that it requires human

⁶ B. Eno, “Generative Music 1.” 1996.

collaboration in order for the musical material to be generated, however this could be at varying levels of involvement, from simply directing a mostly formed musical piece, as in a number of interactive applications^{7 8 9}, to call and response type systems that require almost constant involvement from the user¹⁰ [14] .

Ultimately this research concerns the development of a system which is without a composer or designer to encourage the output towards a certain outcome, and in this sense fits better into the interactive category than the offline one, and while techniques and approaches from offline systems can be useful to understand their applications to real-time, interactive systems, their approaches should be treated separately. This research also aims to explore the space in-between interactive generative systems, and expert agents, in providing real time suggestions that is part of both the performance and realisation of the generative output. This is in contrast to a call and response type system, where the system provides a response to a user input to create two distinct streams of musical events, in the proposed system the generated content and composition process will merge to form a single stream of musical output created by the user and the system concurrently.

2.2.2 Summary of Automatic Composition Techniques

As mentioned above, early procedural composition techniques (that predate computers) often involved the inclusion of stochastic processes into the composition process, in order to remove a level of decision making from the composer, and outsource this to a process. This technique was one of the first used in order to generate music using a computer in the form of the *Illiad Suite*, which was the output of work by Hiller and Isaacson [24], who applied mathematical modelling in the form of random number generation in order to produce a composition for string quartet in four movements, which correspond to four differing techniques that were considered experiments. A contemporary composition, Push Button Bertha [25], which similarly was developed by mathematicians Klein and Bolitho who similarly utilised random processes derived from random number generation, and applied this to a rule based system which accepted or rejected proposed notes based on criteria of acceptable melodies.

More latterly, techniques have diversified to include a number of approaches outside of stochastic, mathematic models that cater to a number of compositional and musical objectives. In their 1999 paper, Papadopoulos and Wiggins [26] categorise the predominant techniques into six categories:

⁷ Opal Limited, "Bloom," 2008. [Online]. Available: <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/bloom/id292792586?mt=8>.

⁸ Radiohead, "Polyfauna," 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/polyfauna/id793263070?mt=8>.

⁹ Björk and Second Wind Ltd. Apps., "Biophilia," 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/björk-biophilia/id434122935?mt=8>.

¹⁰ Google Magenta, "A.I. Duet," 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://aiexperiments.withgoogle.com/ai-duet/%0D>.

- Mathematical models
- Knowledge based systems
- Grammars
- Evolutionary methods
- Systems which learn
- Hybrid systems

While these categories are not definitive; for example, there is distinct crossover between categories, with the rule based approach of Klein and Bolitho fitting into both mathematical and knowledge based categories; they do provide a basic overview of the different approaches used. Mathematical approaches are dealt with first, as has been described above, they were used in the early moments of the research filed. This was primarily down to the low computational cost of the mathematical and stochastic based approaches, that made them suitable for both low-powered early computers, and real-time approaches more latterly, with work by Xenakis [27] and Pachet [8], [9] both later examples of mathematical and stochastic approaches applied to automatic composition.

In particular, Pachet's Continuator demonstrates the real-time applications of mathematical models to music generation, as his system employs Markov models based on melody inputs of a performer. By building up a dictionary of probabilities from a given input, the system can respond in real time, creating a continuation of a given melody that matches harmonically and stylistically. The system also incorporates knowledge based constraints that limit melodic continuations based on traditional melodic compositional techniques, such as phrasing and melodic sequencing. Pachet's system also opens up a new channel of collaboration, by allowing one performer to perform with a system which has learned from input from a completely different performer. The system has since passed a music Turing test¹¹, in which it convinced two music critics, however the validity of this test as a measure of the success of the system has been contested [28], considering Pachet's ambitions for the system are as an improvisational assistant regard the performers assessment as more important than the listener. Similarly, the same criticism mentions that the use of markovian processes is ultimately flawed, given that any rhythmic output depends on the data inputted into the system, meaning that any output will be more likely to imitate rather than generate.

In a similar collaborative, interactive system, Biles [29] explored the use of genetic algorithms, an example of an evolutionary method, to generate an interactive jazz improviser which generates melodies based on the feedback of a mentor. By representing melodic phrases as 8 bit strings, new melodic material can be created based on a fitness value which is determined by the manual feedback of a human listener. While the output is significantly varied, there is a significant bottleneck in the approach, as the fitness function requires a human to evaluate every single iteration of every generation, and brings up significant questions about the evaluation of melodic phrases. Biles acknowledges that the evaluation of melody is ultimately ambiguous, and opts for a human fitness function as the system is designed to be an accompaniment to a human, so an

¹¹ Sony CSL-Paris, "Musical Turing test with the Continuator on VPRO Channel (Amsterdam)," YouTube, 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ynPWOMzossI>.

improvisational partner built on the preferences of his partner makes sense. However, Biles recognises that a human fitness function comes at the cost of the complexity of the system, as melody strings must be simplified to fit into a smaller bit string in order to be evaluated efficiently. This leads to a simplification of the output of the system, which ultimately is rhythmically naïve, as it only has a temporal resolution of a quaver, which is relatively large.

While both Pachet’s Continuator and Biles’ GenJam take distinct approaches to the task, both systems concern the development of an agent that responds to a human melody, ultimately forming a call and response type performance. While both can also be performed in a stand-alone mode – meaning both systems perform without the need for real time human input – they both involve a virtual performer which is entirely separate from the human performer. While it’s able to collaborate with the systems as a duo, it isn’t possible to step inside the generation and influence the melodic content in real time, which would represent a different level of collaboration between human and machine. Pachet has explored the relationship between creativity and interactive music systems [30], broadly focussing on what he calls “reflexive systems”, in which he sets out a number of interaction protocols with interactive systems, all of which are based on collaborative models where the performer and system are separate entities. Of course, it should be acknowledged that this research was performed with The Continuator in mind, so is more of an appraisal of the Continuator’s effect on creativity, rather than an inclusive review of interactive systems in general.

Figure 1. Pachet’s 5 modes of interaction with a reflexive system. [30]

More latterly, a number of practitioners have begun to explore the use of recurrent neural networks (RNNs) as the primary generation technique, with the Google Magenta project¹² being one of the most prominent advocates, using Google’s open source TensorFlow library¹³ for data flow computing, typically used to construct neural networks. Basing their models on a number of image processing techniques [31]–[33], the project aspires to explore the use of computational models to generate art. One of the first experiments released using Google Magenta code, was the AI Duet [23], which provides a similar experience to Pachet’s Continuator by providing a

¹² Google Inc., “Google Magenta,” 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://magenta.tensorflow.org>. [Accessed: 20-Jul-2004].

¹³ Google Inc., “TensorFlow,” 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tensorflow.org/>. [Accessed: 01-Apr-2017].

response to any melody which it is presented. In its form at the time of writing, the application is fairly basic, and any melodic continuations resemble only basic features of any input melody. While the system is not explicitly designed to handle formal musical information, such as key and rhythmic information, the implementation of the neural network begins to recognise some musical features. In this sense, a RNN approach will be able to deal with the criticisms of Pachet's markovian approach, which depends on the input material to produce the outputs, and is likely to produce more original output material.

Similarly, the FlowMachines project by Sony-CSL has also explored the use of neural networks, in this case in the generation of polyphonic chorales in the style of Bach [34]. They propose that the task of generation polyphonic material poses different challenges to monophonic melodies in that a number of different elements must combine to create a homogenous and coherent piece. They argue that "agonistic" – ie approaches that do not need any formal knowledge of harmony – approaches are suited to neural networks, and these provide promising results. Implemented using Keras and Tensorflow, they produce neural networks based on statistical models in order to predict a note in relation to some neighbours. In addition to this, they allow users to impose constraints on the system, which they argue is not common in many probabilistic models. While the output of the system performs well in Turing-style comparative tests, the system is highly optimised to a very niche output of Bach chorales, which the researchers conceive is a particularly homogenous style.

2.2.3 Automatic Composition, Melody Generation & Jazz

A number of researchers have applied generative processes to jazz music; as is part of the motivation of this research, jazz is often seen as a suitable genre for exploring in terms of improvisational systems as improvisation is such an important aspect of jazz music. In this sense, there are a number of interactive and real-time generative systems that utilise jazz. As mentioned above, a prominent example is Biles' GenJam [29], which deals with the collaborative and improvisational aspects of jazz by creating a performance partner for Biles, which mainly performs in a call-and-response style fashion, reacting to input phrases from the human performer.

In a non-real-time system, Pachet, Roy and Papadopoulos [35], [36] have developed a system for generating jazz leadsheets, in the form of monophonic melodies with corresponding chord annotations using markov constraints to control the generation. By utilising a number of constraints, such as meter, note onset and chain order length, generations can be steered in such a way that produces stylistically consistent material while avoiding issues such as accidental plagiarism and repetitiveness. A more recent example, which explores the application of neural networks to jazz generation, is deepjazz¹⁴, which, similar to DeepBach [34], utilises Keras and Theano to build a long term short memory recurrent neural network that generates jazz music. By learning from MIDI files, deepjazz takes advantages of human creative processes to generate human-like jazz music.

¹⁴ J.-S. Kim, "deepjazz: deep learning for jazz," 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://deepjazz.io>.

2.3 Interaction

2.3.1 Digital Lutherie

The field of musical interaction and musical interfaces has been a burgeoning one for a number of years. The crossover between human computer interaction and musical performance systems has spawned a wide-ranging research field incorporating audio synthesis, electronics and computer vision. The outputs range from physical performance art [37] to commercially released interfaces for music production and interaction [38] and has paved the way for a flourishing international conference¹⁵. Since the advent of electronic music, the interaction method for musical performance has been abstracted from the means of sound production, allowing for a wide range of interaction technologies to be applied to music performance. The earliest prominent example of a specifically designed, electronic music would be the Theremin [39]; an electronic instrument which is controlled through two proximity sensors that allow a user to control the pitch and the volume of the instrument without directly touching it.

A landmark publication in the field, yielding the title of this section, is Sergi Jordá's Digital Lutherie [40]; a wide ranging review of the field that sets out a declaration of the principles that should be followed when developing interactive musical systems and interfaces for musical expression. Digital Lutherie works to conceptually define what a digital instrument is, and endeavours to translate the concepts of physical lutherie and traditional instrument learning and musical expression to the digital domain. He suggests that the relationship between human and computer is key to developing and improving interactive systems, and that a balance between discarding the negative aspects of traditional instruments and maintaining positive aspects is also key to developing musical interaction. By setting out a formalised set of principles for not only the development of digital instruments, but the research and study of them too, Digital Lutherie has established a precedent for future research in the field, and is a key publication for any musical interaction research.

Golan Levin also dealt with the conceptual basis for interfaces for musical performance, in his work which tackled the metaphors that are used for interface design, and their expressive capacity [41]. He proposed a new, abstract metaphor that allows for the simultaneous creation of performance imagery and sound which comprises of an imaginary audiovisual substance that can be used to create audiovisuals in real time. In particular, he aims to create a basis for an "*Instantly Knowable, Indefinitely Masterable Interface*" that is concurrently easy to learn, yet powerful, with a pencil and a piano given as two examples of existing interface metaphors which match this brief. He measures the expressive capability of his metaphors by producing five differing audiovisual systems, and then observing their learnability, predictability, expressivity and granularity. This research provides a solid theoretical basis in which to closer map expected interactions with expressive outputs, and helps to define what modern audiovisual systems should aspire to.

¹⁵ "NIME | International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression." [Online]. Available: <http://www.nime.org>.

2.3.2 Beyond the Keyboard

As such a common method of musical input, the keyboard is ubiquitous in music creation and performance tools, from piano rolls in DAWs, to the input for web apps along with the most commonly accepted means of control for synthesisers. The strong visual and intuitive interface of a traditional keyboard, along with the familiarity that it maintains for both musicians and non-musicians, it makes sense that the keyboard metaphor is translated into digital instruments. However, in lieu of new technologies that deal with the shortcoming of the keyboard, researchers have been exploring methods of augmenting the limitations of the traditional keyboard as is afforded by modern interaction technologies.

Grosshauser & Tröster [42] have explored the use of a pressure sensor in order to add an additional dimension of interaction to a traditional keyboard. By measuring the force and torque on a piano key when pressed by a performer, opening up a new interface for performance with a traditional keyboard by extending it with sensors. Yang & Essl [43] have also explored extending the capabilities of the existing keyboard with additional interaction methods, in this case by using a Microsoft Kinect to detect gestural data via the depth sensor in the Kinect. Instead of using this interaction to change the musical content that the keyboard produces, they allow a user to change sonic parameters, such as synthesiser controls, with the gestures.

The most prominent commercially available product that deals with extending the keyboard is Roli's Seaboard [38], which primarily deals with the discrete nature of traditional keyboard keys by providing a number of options for producing pitches between the discrete notes in a more intuitive way than a traditional pitch wheel. The Seaboard is comprised of flexible, rubber keys, which allow for independent vibrato on each key, augmenting the static frequency of the traditional keyboard. This allows a performer to achieve timbres and performances that would normally only be possible with string instruments, and a number of promotional videos from Roli contain musicians mimicking guitar solos with the instrument, with impressive results¹⁶. In addition to the vibrato element, a Seaboard also contains a contact strip, which allows for legato like movement between multiple notes at once independent of each other. This provides greater control than a pitch wheel, as a pitch wheel changes the pitch of all played notes at once, which limits the performance capabilities of the user. While the Seaboard deals well with the pitch limitations of a traditional keyboard in a physical form factor, it doesn't translate at all well to a digital interface. The touch screen version of the Seaboard¹⁷ includes both the indiscrete note boundaries and pitch bending capabilities, but without the tactile feedback of the rubber keys to anchor the centre of each note, accuracy becomes impossible as the entire screen becomes a sliding pitch scale.

¹⁶ ROLI, Marco Parisi plays Jimi Hendrix's "Little Wing" on the Seaboard RISE at Musikmesse 2016. 2016. Available <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jh-hzbG5Fzl>.

¹⁷ ROLI Ltd., "Seaboard 5D," 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://itunes.apple.com/us/app/seaboard-5d/id1173937855?mt=8>.

2.3.3 Touch Screen Interfaces

As alluded to in the introduction to this research, devices with touch screens are widely available in the developed world, and represent an opportunity to develop an interface that responds to a basic and intuitive form of interaction in the form of touch and gesture. There are a number of examples of research that have explored the use of touch screen devices in the search for new interfaces for musical expression which provide a solid basis for the interface for this research.

Following on from their research mentioned above, Yang & Essl have also explored the user of multi-touch on mobile devices [44], in this case to present a visual programming language with which users can use to create controllers for musical input. While the application is novel and provides an engaging way to create software synthesisers, the user of a touch screen device does not appear to be utilised other than as a simpler means of interfacing with the visual language. If, for example, gestural input had been considered as a potential augmentation to the input, newer interactions could have been afforded.

In contrast, Rub Synth [45] explores the lack of necessity to exert physical force on a touch screen in order to interact with it, and cite this as a reason for diminished enjoyment or engagement in touch screen interfaces. In order to deal with this, the researcher proposes a novel interface in which the performer has to constantly move their finger on the screen in order to produce sound. While the implication that physical exertion is essential to performance satisfaction with a musical instrument is doubtful, a novel interaction method such as this provides an intuitive way to interact with a touch screen device, and the sensations and gestures it would produce in the performer could have potential to induce novel performance methods as well.

Pitch Canvas [46] attempts to combat the use of real-world interface metaphors for touch screen instruments by developing a novel interface for musical expression on a touch screen. By mapping the pitch space to a hexagonal map, the researchers are able to create an environment where a user can explore pitches with their finger. In addition to this, a number of gestures are mapped to performance parameters, such as legato phrasing and vibrato, which add additional modes of control to the interface for performers.

2.4 Summary of the State of the Art

Following on from the above observations of existing research, the knowledge gathered will be summarised below, and the consequences of this to the current research will be discussed.

2.4.1 Summary of Cognitive Theory of Melody

The above research clearly demonstrates that the IR model can be applied to both analysis and predictive modelling with tentative applications to composition and melody generation, but have yet to be explored extensively as the basis of a knowledge based system that enables an expert agent for performance and compositional tools. The above research focusses mainly on the

evaluation and empirical testing of the IR model, however there appears to be an opportunity to study the use of the IR model to induce rule based constraints on a probabilistic melody generation system, in a combination of melody expectancy and melody generation research. Any melody generation system should have grounding in the perceptual basis of melody, and Narmour's IR model has been validated as a step towards a fundamental understanding of universal aspects of melody.

Another relevant area of research related to this project is the application of the IR model to jazz melodies. The top-down processes set out in Narmour's original research are intended to account for a variability in stylistic variables, however as the IR model exists on the basic premise that expected intervals should be realised, and the focus of this project is on jazz - a style heavily dependent on improvisation and unpredictability in the performance and composition of melodic themes - this seems to present an interesting research opportunity to observe the IR model's suitability to jazz, in particular a live, improvisational model, paving the way for a more universal model.

While Pearce's proposed model for composition modelling and expectancy does provide a more universal model than the IR model, ultimately Schellenberg's amendments to the IR model as well as the work taken to give numerical value to results of the IR analyses, the IR model in this case will be the most suitable model to provide a perceptual basis of melody to the project.

2.4.2 Summary of Melody Generation

Following on from the definition of terms within the literature, it appears the output of this project is best described as an interactive music system that can be more specifically defined as a performance-based generative instrument. There are a number of methods that have been applied to the field of algorithmic composition with promising results, and while it appears that recurrent neural networks are currently providing the best results in terms of offline composition, for the purposes of this project it appears that Markov chains will be the most appropriate generation method. This is due to the low computational cost of running the models, which helps reduce latency and increase the ability to perform with the system.

While there are a number of examples of systems that have generated jazz content, including a few that explore improvisational systems, there are none that have applied melody generation to a performance system in real time, so it appears there's a gap in the current research that can be explored.

2.4.3 Summary of Interaction

Following on from the above research, it's clear that it's important to consider the interface metaphor used to interact with the system, as well as the relationship between the user and the computer in generation and realising the melody. It's clear that real-world interfaces are no longer relevant, and provide needless limitations when used as metaphors for touchscreens and digital interfaces. In addition to this, it's clear that the constraints the system puts on the user are important, as they should maximise the expressivity afforded to the user, while avoiding

overwhelming complexity to non-musical users. In following this, the system should aspire to Golan's "*Instantly Knowable, Indefinitely Masterable Interface*".

3 Methodology

3.1 Methodology Overview

In order to fulfil the aims of the project, the instrument was split into three component parts that comprise the overall system. The three parts have a cyclical relationship, whereby each component sends and receives relevant information. The first of these is the melody generation module, which receives chains of melodies with their harmonic context, and outputs five note suggestions, which are sent to the interface. The second module, the interface, receives these suggestions, and allows for the user to choose between them. When a user has chosen a suggestion, the chosen note is sent to the third module, the sound engine, which synthesises the note and makes it audible. Additionally, the note is fed back into the melody generation module in order to produce new suggestions.

Figure 2. Visual representation of relationship between modules

Although this project concerns the development of an application for touch screen devices, the system was developed using technologies for desktop applications for agility and ease of development. This acts as a proof of concept, as the system can easily be adapted to function on a touch screen device, but does not currently work as a touch screen application.

3.2 Melody Generation

After considering a number of methods of generation, Markov chains were chosen to provide note suggestions to the system. This was due to the low computing overhead required to implement Markov chains, making them perfect for a real-time application such as this. In addition to this, Markov chains are excellent at producing imitations of styles, due to their architecture and intake of pre-composed material.

In building the system, it was important to consider the key aspects of jazz improvisation, such as melodic and harmonic flexibility. It is common in jazz improvisation for improvised melodies to be very tightly matched to the accompanying chord harmonically. In addition to this, the

surrounding harmonic context can often be rapidly changing, leading to complex melodic patterns that can cross over multiple keys and scales within a single phrase. As is consistent with the aims of the project, in order to allow the system to fit a number of applications and to be as adaptable as possible, it was determined that the system would provide five different suggestions to the user at every point. These would be notes that are relative to the previous note played, with two suggestions containing notes higher than the previous note, two lower than the previous note, and the previous note always included as well.

Python was used for the melody generation module due to its suitability for use with data speed with large groups of numbers, which are used to generate the melodies.

3.2.1 Materials

In order to build the Markov chains that were required for the system, it was necessary to source representations of jazz melodies in a format that could be used to build such a system. These representations ultimately needed to include the melody in MIDI notes, along with the accompanying harmonic context at the time of each melodic note. Also, it was necessary to source a collection of a decent size in order to account for a sufficiently large number of harmonic circumstances, as well as to provide appropriate variation in the output of the system. To these ends, a number of sources were considered, including jazz melody transcriptions from The Jazzomat Project¹⁸, but ultimately as these representations only consist of automatically transcribed versions of jazz solos, and lack the harmonic context that is required for the models, MIDI representations of jazz standards were chosen. A number of MIDI representations of jazz standards are widely available, however ultimately Real Book jazz standards from the software Band-In-A-Box¹⁹ were chosen, as it was possible to render harmonic reductions of the standards. This was particularly useful for building the models, as the chord at the moment of each new melody note could be extracted easily, which was crucial in building the models.

The image shows a musical score for guitar and piano. The guitar part is in the top staff, starting at measure 34. It features a melodic line with various note values, including a triplet of eighth notes. The piano accompaniment is shown in two staves below the guitar. The right hand of the piano (Pno. Treble Clef) plays reduced chords, while the left hand (Pno. Bass Clef) plays a simple bass line. The key signature has one sharp (F#), and the time signature is 4/4.

Figure 3. Example of reduced chords and melody

¹⁸ University of Music FRANZ LISZT Weimar, "The Jazzomat Research Project," 2013. [Online]. Available: <http://jazzomat.hfm-weimar.de>.

¹⁹ PG Music, "Band-in-a-Box® 2017." 2017. Available: <http://www.pgmusic.com>.

Once the harmonically reduced standards were obtained, they were then processed using the chord detection and symbolic analysis tools in the Giant Steps API²⁰ in order to get a simple, text based representation of the chords and notes that could be interpreted by Python. These representations were then saved to csv files that contained the start time, end time, midi note and accompanying chord for every note of the melody.

newKey	chord	startTime	pitch	duration	originalKey
C	Amin7	0.04166666666666664	67	1.825	F
C	C9	2.075	65	0.5249999999999999	F
C	C9	3.025	64	0.5333333333333332	F
C	F9	4.041666666666667	67	1.375	F
C	F9	5.733333333333333	67	1.8583333333333334	F
C	Amin7	8.025	67	0.43333333333333357	F
C	Amin7	8.691666666666666	64	0.40000000000000036	F
C	Amin7	9.041666666666666	60	0.49166666666666714	F
C	Amin7	9.7	55	3.783333333333333	F
C	A7	14.016666666666666	69	1.7083333333333334	F
C	Dmin7	16.058333333333334	67	0.5249999999999986	F

Figure 4. Example of processed melody csv

It's important to note that these representations only include the pre-composed melodies that exist in the head of the standards, so while the system is an improvisational system, it will be built on composed melodies and not transcribed solos. In an ideal situation, the source material would be a combination of jazz standards and solo transcriptions, such as from the jazz-o-mat project, but this would take a significant amount of work to build source materials including harmonic context, which was out of scope for this research.

3.2.2 Implementation

As one of the key hurdles to overcome was the variability of jazz improvisation, and the regularly changing harmonic context, it was critical to devise a system that could adapt to these rapidly changing contexts, and still provide harmonically and stylistically consistent suggestions. The most relevant previous example was Pachet's work on variable order Markov chains [8], [9], which dealt with such a problem by allowing the system to vary the order of the Markov chain used as input to the model, which in turn allowed the system to become flexible to the complexity of the situation in which it is applied. Taking inspiration from this, the system was built to allow variation not only the length of the input Markov chain, but to also simultaneously vary the complexity of the information representing the harmonic context, which means the output could be suitably flexible to the situation as well as provide high quality output. In order to make this possible, four different models of generation were developed, each with a differing level of complexity in terms

²⁰ The GiantSteps Project, "GiantSteps API," 2016. [Online]. Available: https://github.com/GiantSteps/GS_API.

of the input information it receives. By allowing the system to dynamically switch between the different models when a more complex model is unable to provide an output, the system can efficiently produce suggestions that take into account as much information as is possible at each moment in the use of the system.

Each of the four models takes an input chain of four events, which it then uses to search through dictionaries to find corresponding chains that are stored in the system, and provides the continuations of those chains to help generate the suggestions. The complex model is the primary model, that takes into account the most amount of information in both the chain, and instantaneous context in order to generate suggestions. This model receives chains of four notes, and the exact chord at the time that each of those four notes were played. In addition to this, the model takes into account the chord at the moment of generation.

Figure 5. A visual representation of the Complex Model, where the grey circles represent previously played notes as MIDI notes, with the accompanying chord below. The white circle represents the current state, with the current chord displayed at the bottom.

The second model, named the Reduced Chord Model, uses a similar methodology to the complex model, in the sense that it takes into account harmonic information at each step in the chain, as well as the current chord. However, with this model the harmonic information is less specific, as all chords are simplified into major or minor chords. For example, an Amin7 chord would be simplified to an A minor chord, which would provide a greater variety of suggestions than if it was more specific, but they are less well suited to the specific context they describe. By including the chords at each step in the chain, the model is still relatively complex, and is likely to provide high quality suggestions, but less consistent with original melodies as the Complex model.

Figure 6. Reduced Chord Model

The third model is named the Single Chord model, and is different to the previous two models in the sense that it doesn't take into account any harmonic information in the input chain, however it does take into account the chord at the moment of generation. As the current chord is the most important to jazz improvisation, this model represents one that can still produce stylistically consistent suggestions, but is unlikely to provide suggestions as coherent as the previous two models, which are more likely to produce melodies which follow chord changes.

Figure 7. Single Chord Model

The fourth and final model is the Simple Model, which simply takes the MIDI values into account with no regard for the harmonic context. As this model doesn't take any harmonic information into account, it is not tied to any key information, so when a piece modulates keys, this model will not follow the changes, so will most likely produce suggestions that are not consistent with the harmonic context. For these reasons, this model acts as a fall-back model which will always provide suggestions when there are no further continuations from the other models.

Figure 8. Simple Model

When a new note is presented to the system, it is added to the existing chain to produce a four note and chord chain, which is then inputted into the system along with the complex representation of the current chord. The notes of the chain are then converted into chroma, and all of the chord representations are converted into simple representations of the chords. From these conversions, the four different chains required for the models are generated. The new note – as a MIDI value, not a chroma – is then added to an array representing the new suggestions from the system, as the current note is always included as an option, and the system begins to find two notes above, and two notes below that note. It begins by searching at the longest chain length of the first model, and attempts to extract continuations from this chain. In the example of the complex model, the four-element chain, and the current chord, is used as a search query in a dictionary which contains continuations of previous chains from the source material. If the system finds a match for the input chain, it then adds it to an array representing potential suggestions from the model. The system will always try to fill up as many suggestions as possible with the current model before moving on, so in the current example, if the most complex model at the longest chain length returned two continuations above the current note, and two continuations below the current note, the system would provide these as the outputs, and end the generation process. However, as is more common, the system is likely to find that the chain length and model complexity will only be able to provide an incomplete number of suggestions. In the case that the required number of suggestions required are not produced, the system will first begin to reduce the chain length of the first model – in this example it would take the complex model, and provide it with a third order chain in attempt to extract further suggestions. If the system gets to the first order chain of this model, and still cannot provide the required number of suggestions from the system, it will then switch to the next model, and begin the process at the fourth order chain.

A standard chain length of the fourth order was determined to be the most suitable length to provide a balance between the highest quality suggestions, while allowing the model to load

efficiently and avoid reproducing the source material. When testing the generator separate to the interface, it was found that even with very short chain lengths, when given a chord sequence from a standard form within the source material, the generator would almost exactly reproduce the melody. Given that the extra information allows for very specific circumstances, it became clear that long chain lengths would be unnecessary, so a fourth order chain was chosen as a good middle ground.

Following this process, the system will always default to the most complex representations and longest chain lengths to produce suggestions, but will dynamically switch between models and chain lengths in order to provide the five suggestions required.

3.3 Interaction Design

The interface module of the system consists of two alternative interfaces, that both utilise different methods of interaction, but use exactly the same melody generation module, and communicate in mostly the same way. One uses elements of an existing interface metaphor – the traditional keyboard – while the other presents a new interface metaphor. The development of two distant interfaces allows a comparison between two drastically different interaction methods, and allows the observation of user behaviour in both familiar and unfamiliar situations. Both interfaces were developed in visual design language Processing and both communicate with the melody generation module using Open Sound Control (OSC), and they both receive the five note suggestions as MIDI values to be presented visually, and send note and chord pairs whenever a new note is played.

3.3.1 Intervallic Keyboard Model

This interface utilises an already existing interface metaphor, in the shape of the traditional keyboard, with some alterations to make it better utilise the affordances of a touch screen device. As a keyboard is a well-known musical interface, that most in the western world will be familiar with, these familiarities will help allow the interface to be understood intuitively with as small a learning period as is possible.

One of the key deficiencies identified in existing keyboard metaphor interfaces was the small size of key, which makes performing accurately at speed more difficult, especially when considering that the user has no tactile feedback to orientate themselves positionally. In order to confront this issue, the Intervallic Keyboard Model uses only five, large keys which represent the five suggestions from the melody generation model explicitly. This means that the central key always represents the previous note played, and the two keys to the left of centre represent notes lower than the previous note, and the two keys to the right of centre represent notes higher than the previous note. This represents a difference with the traditional keyboard model, as the keys don't move spatially, but the notes they represent are constantly changing; for example, if a user pressed the central key continuously, they would play a string of exactly the same notes, but if they continuously pressed the key to the right of the central key, they would play an indefinitely rising phrase, without changing keys. This presents a change to the users' relationship between

action and result in terms of direction and pitch, as expected behaviours from traditional interfaces are now challenged, as instead of the direction of movement being directly linked to the direction of the melody, this relationship is now relative, as it is the position of the key relative to the central key which represents the direction of the melody.

Figure 9: The Intervallic Keyboard Interface

In order to allow the user to be more informed about the notes that the keys represent, the interface includes a visualisation showing the location of the five suggestions on a traditional keyboard, which updates in sync with the playable keys above. Both the playable keys and the keyboard visualisation display quality values for the suggestions via colour coding, with each key coloured either red, yellow or green. The quality value is rendered from the melody generation process, and considers the complexity of the model, and the chain length used to generate the particular note. For example, a note generated using a long chain length from the complex model would be considered the highest quality, given that it has used to most information from the source material and the context to generate it, so it is coloured green to indicate this to the user. However, if the note has come from the simple model, and has not taken into account any contextual information, it will be coloured red, indicating to the user that it is of a lower quality.

The Intervallic Keyboard represents a novel interface for touch screen devices which maps the outputs of the Melody Generation module directly onto a screen in a way that incorporates familiar ideas to both expert and novice musicians, but still challenges current paradigms. The use of a relative relationship to pitch movement instead of direct could present initial difficulties, particularly in those who are particularly familiar with a traditional keyboard, so this may present a learning period to adjust. Despite this, the user is concurrently given the ability to accurately travel a great deal of notes accurately, which is traditionally not possible for keyboard style touch screen apps, while also making efficient use of the screen real estate available. It is a well-supported idea that imposing constraints upon a user can aid creativity [47][48], so it is possible that by imposing the

constraint of restriction of note choices upon users, even those who are musically experienced, there could be an enhancement in their creativity.

3.3.2 Contour Model

The second interface takes an alternative approach to the Intervallic Keyboard model, in the sense that it eschews the use of a traditional interface metaphor, and instead presents a novel musical interface for a touch screen device. There are a number of interactions that a touch screen can afford, such as pinches, drags and swipes, that are left unused. This model allows a user to perform melodies by directly drawing melody contours onto the screen, which are then interpreted into steps between the five note suggestions outputted from the melody generation module. A note begins to sound when the user places their finger on the screen, and can move the melody up by dragging up on the y axis, and down by dragging down on the y axis, and a continuous note will remain if they keep their finger in the same place. The interface displays a trail of the contour they have drawn (see Figure 10), as a visualisation of the melody that has been previously played.

Figure 10: The Contour Interface

The interface divides the screen up into 14 vertical zones (see Figure 11), which are used to track the distance and speed of users' gestures. When a user has a finger pressed down, the interface determines the closest zone on the axis, and when the user moves to a different vertical zone without lifting their finger, this is recognised as a movement. However, if the user stays within one vertical zone, despite moving a small distance in the y axis, no movement is detected and a continuous note is heard. After a movement has been detected, the system determines how many vertical zones have been crossed, in a single direction, within a determined movement time

threshold, which has been set at 50ms. Through experimentation, 50ms was established as the most suitable threshold, as it allows sufficient time for a user to make a large movement before the time ends, while being short enough to allow for smooth and continuous melodies. It had been found that shorter times allowed for more continuous melodies, however in most cases large movements were missed, as small gestures were recognised before the user had finished the movement. When the gesture is completed, if it has crossed two or more zones, this is determined to be a large movement, and thus represents the largest of the suggestions in either direction. If the gesture crossed only one zone, the gesture is interpreted as small, and the smallest suggestion is returned.

Figure 11: The Contour Interface with vertical zones visible

Users can also create melodies in a more discrete fashion, without drawing onto the screen and playing each note individually by pressing on different zones in the y axis. Using a similar, relative basis to the Intervallic Keyboard model, the distance the press is, on the y axis, from the centre is determined, and then this is used to select one of the five note suggestions. For example, if a user presses a number of times in the centre of the screen, each time the same note will be played, however if they press further up the y axis, an ascending melody will be performed. By using this method, more discrete and staccato melodies can be performed, as well as faster travel up scales. In contrast to the Intervallic Keyboard model, this interface allows the user to have a direct relationship with the pitch, as their movements are closely mapped to the direction of the melody at every step.

Figure 12: An example of a staccato, and non-continuous melody

In contrast to the Intervallic Keyboard model, this interface performs the role of interpreter between the performer and the melody generator, and distances the user from having such a direct relationship with the notes that they choose as with the Intervallic Keyboard model. This can have two effects on the user; first, that there is a layer of the “illusion of control” created by the gesture interpretation of the system. Without being provided an explanation of how the gestural system works, the user will not have any understanding of how their movements are mapped to a limited set of possibilities, so this can give the user a greater sense of control, despite having the same amount of control as with the other interface. The second is that the user has less readily available information about the notes that they are choosing, as with the colour coded keys and keyboard visualisation with the Intervallic Keyboard model, so the user is forced to put a level of trust in the system and the output of the melody generation, and give up an element of control. This may better suit users who are not experienced musicians, as they are more likely to not need to feel fully in control of each and every note they play, however this may challenge more experienced musicians, who may miss the decision-making aids of the previous interface.

3.4 Sound Engine

The sound engine is the final module of the system, and is implemented in supercollider where OSCdef objects receive OSC messages from the interface whenever a new note is suggested, which is then synthesised and played on the audio server. When a new note is received, a melodySynth variable is assigned to a new SynthDef, which is passed the fundamental frequency of the new note, which is converted from the MIDI value which is passed from Processing. Note on and note off messages are used to instruct the sound engine to create and kill the corresponding SynthDefs.

The sound engine also synthesises chords, which are coordinated in Processing, and receives chord OSC messages periodically. Chords are played continuously, and are only changed when a new chord OSC message is received. The OSC messages consist of chord names stored as strings, and these are then used as a reference to a dictionary of chords, which then returns the chord as an array of MIDI values, which are then synthesised with SynthDefs.

4 Evaluation

In order to evaluate the system as a whole, it's necessary to understand the suitability of each of the components individually, as well as their combined performance. To these ends, the evaluation was performed to first evaluate the output of the melody generator in isolation, before performing user evaluations in order to understand the system in totality. By combining both qualitative and quantitative evaluations, it was possible to get a full perspective of the system's performance with respect to the aims of the project.

4.1 Melody Evaluation

The output of the melody generator can be isolated by generating offline melodies that are fed with pre-composed chord sequences. This means that the melody generator can be evaluated empirically on its own, and this section sets out the ambitions of that evaluation. The testing of the melody generation module primarily surrounds the comparative performance of the different generation models which comprise the system. By assigning comparable values to each of the models, an empirical basis can be established for the hierarchy of models which the system goes through in order to generate melodies, thus improving the output of the system as a whole.

Defining what constitutes a high-quality melody computationally is fraught with difficulties, first due to the subjectivity of melody perception, as well as issues of style and aesthetic that can alter external perspectives of melodies. However, by combining a human, subjective evaluation with a computational evaluation which uses a model for human perception of melody, namely Narmour's IR model in this case, we can alleviate these issues significantly, and provide a robust evaluation of the output of the melody generation, that is tailored to the current project. Based on the principle that the original melodies from the source material were the target in terms of harmonic structure and complexity, therefore samples of the original melodies should be used as a baseline from which to compare any generated melodies. Inferred from this, we can presume that the more similar a generated melody is, the higher quality it should be deemed, in terms of this evaluation. From this basis, the hypothesis is that generative models that use more complex representations of the source materials will produce melodies that are closer, or more similar, to original jazz melodies. In this sense, it would be expected that the Complex model will produce melodies that are more similar to the originals, while the Simple model will produce less similar melodies. Between the Simple Chord model and the Single Chord model, it is not clear which uses more complex information, as the Single Chord model uses more complex chord notation, while the Simple Chord model uses chords during every step of the chain, and not just at the

moment of generation. The computation and human evaluation will help to shine light on which of these two produce melodies more consistent with the originals.

4.1.1 Computational Evaluation

To prepare melodies to be tested by the computational evaluation, it was necessary to make small adaption to the melody generation module of the system, in order to allow it to generate melodies in an offline mode, that were isolated to an individual generation model. In order to do this, the system was given chord sequences from existing melodies in the source materials, and was prompted to generate notes at the rhythmic points in the existing files were the previous melody was. Twenty-four of the original jazz standards were chosen at random, twelve of which were used as bassline example melodies from which the others were compared, and twelve which were used as guides to generate melodies, following the process above. Originally, the same standards that were used for comparison were also used to generate the melodies, however due to the specific nature of the harmonic changes, it came to be that the original melodies were often reproduced almost exactly, rendering the experiment useless, so it was determined there should be no crossover between reference melodies, and chord sequences for generating new melodies.

In order to derive melodic similarity computationally, inspiration was taken from Grachten and Arcos' research using principles from Narmour's IR model to derive a similarity measure [11]. Following on from this, we can assume that melodies that achieve similar expectancy values from Narmour's IR model can be assumed to be similar in their melodic structure and intervallic pattern. In order to apply this computationally, a version of the expectancy modelling from Narmour's IR model, implemented in the MIDI toolbox²¹ for matLAB was used. The MIDI toolbox implementation allows for the calculation of values of expectancy for each interval of a melody for six of Narmour's original principles, although it utilises Schellenberg's updated rules for three of the principles (registral direction, registral return and proximity) and Krumhansl's amendments for consonance. For each prepared melody, as described above, an expectancy value was calculated for each of the six principles for every interval, from which a mean is calculated for the whole piece. From this data, the mean of each collection is calculated for each principle, as can be seen in the table in Figure 13.

²¹ University of Jyväskylä, "MIDI Toolbox," 2004. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/miditoolbox>.

	Registral Return	Registral Direction	Intervallic Difference	Closure	Proximity	Consonance
Original	0.04	0.65	0.76	0.70	2.68	5.55
Complex	0.03	0.66	0.75	0.71	2.67	5.57
singleChord	0.03	0.61	0.76	0.69	2.82	5.58
simpleChord	0.03	0.61	0.74	0.70	2.83	5.51
Simple	0.05	0.59	0.76	0.70	3.06	5.67

Figure 13: Average expectancy ratings for each model

From here, the average distance from each expectancy value for each model to the corresponding value in the original standards is calculated, as a percentage of the original value. These values are then averaged to give a mean distance across the six principles, and giving us a distance value, which is visible in Figure 14.

	Registral Return	Registral Direction	Intervallic Difference	Closure	Proximity	Consonance	Average Distance
Complex	0.172	0.014	0.012	0.014	0.004	0.004	0.037
singleChord	0.228	0.055	0.005	0.020	0.049	0.006	0.060
simpleChord	0.188	0.060	0.025	0.001	0.055	0.006	0.056
Simple	0.155	0.092	0.007	0.012	0.139	0.021	0.071

Figure 14: Average distance from original standards

According to the results shown in Figure 14, the hypothesis that more complex models produce melodies that are more similar to original jazz melodies is accurate, given that the Complex model is the generative model that takes into account most information and has the lowest average distance to the originals. According to this evaluation method, the Simple Chord model produces melodies that are closer to the originals than the Single Chord model, which may be reflected in Registral Return and Closure values, which are amongst the values in which this model is closest to the original. The nature of the Simple Model means that it uses simplified harmonic information in the preceding chain, meaning that melody continuations are based on more specific whole chains, which could explain why the Simple Chord model has a shorter distance to the originals than the Single Chord model. As is also expected, the Simple model produces melodies that are furthest from the original melodies, due to the fact that this model does not take into account any further context than the preceding chains of MIDI notes.

4.1.2 Human Melody Appraisal

In order to reinforce and validate the results of the computational melody evaluation, it was necessary to perform a human melody evaluation, to get subjective ratings from real people to compare with the computational rankings. While the computational evaluation focuses on cognitive principles and empirical methods, it doesn't take into account any aesthetic considerations, and as well there is no specificity to jazz, which this human melody evaluation can take into account. In addition to this, additional aspects, such as memorability of the melodies, was tested in order to understand the difference between the models in greater detail.

The experiment took the form of an online survey, which was constructed using Google Forms. For the first section of the survey, users were presented with 8 bar extracts of generated melodies from each model, as well as extracts from the original melodies. The melodies were rendered with software instruments in Logic Pro X from MIDI files to make them audible, and consist of the melody performed with a piano, as well as a simple chord backing. After listening to each extract, users were asked the following three questions with a Likert scale, with the option to give a value between 1 and 10 to each question:

1. How much do you like this melody?
2. How jazzy was this melody?
3. How natural was this melody?

These three questions were chosen to primarily gauge the users' subjective opinion of the melody (via the first question), and then begin to unpack their reasoning with the second two questions. It was decided that it is preferable to explore participants' reasoning for their ratings via Likert scale questions with discrete ratings, rather than open ended answers, as with a long questionnaire users are likely to give attention to open ended answers, and the processing of this data would take significantly more time. Users were given references at the extremes of each scale in order to contextualise the scale (see Figure 15). Users were presented with 10 extracts varying between 10 and 19 seconds in length, and consisted of two examples from each model, along with two original examples.

How natural was this melody?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Not at all natural Very natural

Figure 15: An example of a Likert scale question from the evaluation

In the second section, participants were presented with 9 extracts, of which 5 had been presented to them in the previous section, however these extracts only consist of the melodies, and don't include the accompanying chords. This is to present a small difference to the previous

examples, to encourage users to listen closely to the melody for differences, rather than just sensing similarities from the previous examples. They are then asked to state whether they remember the melodies from the previous section, and are able to answer that either “I definitely remember this melody”, “I somewhat remember this melody” or “I don’t remember this melody at all”. This concludes the survey, after which participants are asked personal information, such as age, gender and musical preferences. Participants are also asked if they recognised any of the extracts from before the experiment, however none of the participants stated that they had.

There were 19 respondents to the survey of which 14 were male, and 5 were female. Their ages ranged from 20 to 66, and three of the respondents declared that they listened to jazz music regularly.

	Subjective Rating	Jazzyness	Naturalness
Original	8.08	6.79	8.05
Complex	5.82	6.76	5.82
SimpleChord	5.61	5.71	5.18
SingleChord	6.66	5.29	4.13
Simple	2.16	5.63	2.24

Figure 16: Average ratings from the participants for each model

After averaging users’ ratings for each of the three questions for both examples for each category, Figure 16 shows the final results from the human melody evaluation. The subjective rating shows a clear preference for the original jazz standard melodies, as well as a naturalness rating that shows a stronger weighting towards the original melodies. At the other extreme, the simple model received subjective ratings and naturalness ratings significantly below the other models, putting its melodies as a clear least favourite of participants. Between the three other models, ratings for preference and naturalness were significantly less diverse, and similarly didn’t show such a strong correlation between subjective rating and naturalness. Ratings for jazzyness showed significantly less variation, although generally there was a general correlation with subjective rating, as participants tended to rate melodies higher that they also rated as jazzier. Similarly, ratings for jazzyness and naturalness correlated.

	Definitely Remembered	Somewhat Remembered	Not Remembered
Original	42.1%	26.3%	31.6%
Complex	21.1%	36.8%	42.1%
SimpleChord	15.8%	52.6%	31.6%
SingleChord	21.1%	47.4%	31.6%
Simple	21.1%	26.3%	52.6%

Figure 17: Percentage each answer for memory questions

The memorableness ratings (Figure 17) provide significantly less correlation than the subjectivity ratings, aside from that the original melodies appear significantly more memorable than those generated by the models. The Complex, Single Chord and Simple models all achieved the same percentage of responses saying they definitely remembered the melody, and the percentages declaring they didn't remember the melody at all is uncorrelated, with percentages varying. It should be noted that there was only one real example of each melody that participants could potentially remember, so the sample size for each model is relatively small, which in this case could lead to data that is less reliable than that with larger sample sizes, as with the first portion of the experiment. Performing this portion of the experiment with more samples of melodies that participants had previously been exposed to would have led to more usable results, and as it is, there are no definitive conclusions to draw about the memorability of the melodies.

4.1.3 Summary of Melody Evaluation

By performing two types of melody evaluation, one computational and one with human test subjects, the output of the melody generator has been stringently evaluated, and the results from the two evaluations can be cross validated in order to corroborate their reliability.

According to the methodology of the computational evaluation, melodies generated by the complex model were most similar to original, jazz standard melodies, and the simple model generated melodies that were least close to the original melodies. This is partly corroborated by the human melody evaluation, which found that the melodies from the simple model are least like subjectively, as well as view as the least natural of the four models. Similarly, the naturalness ratings from the human evaluation correlate exactly with the distance rankings from the computational evaluation, suggesting that naturalness. The suggested rankings from the subjective evaluation would suggest that the Single Chord model is most preferred model, followed by the Complex and Simple Chord models, however this should be taken with a pinch of salt considering that participants were only exposed to two short extracts from each model

Resulting from this, it has been determined that the hierarchy of the generative models that make up the melody generation module should be as follows:

1. Complex Model
2. Simple Chord Model
3. Single Chord Model
4. Simple Model

Memory tests showed inconsistent results that did not correlate with results from either evaluation, and as such are treated as inconclusive. In order to achieve more coherent results from a memory type experiment, participants would need to be exposed to a number of different examples of melodies from each model to increase the overall sample size for each participant.

4.2 User Tests

In order to provide a qualitative evaluation of the system as a whole, it was necessary to perform user tests to observe the system in use in a use-case scenario. Inspiration was taken from HCI evaluation, and the applications of this approach to musical projects[49] were taken into account as well.

4.2.1 Approach

For a standard HCI evaluation, it's common to request that participants complete a functional task, such as completing an action, which represents the action that the user is expected to undertake in normal situations. By measuring how well or easily the user completed this task, you can then evaluate the suitability of the interface for facilitating this task. However, as the expected outcome of this interface is to be used as a creative tool, the overall task is not as inherently clear as in a functional interface as would be more common in HCI evaluation. To this end, the human evaluation has been split into two sections which allow for a task based test as well as a freer, exploration style test, which allow for more standard HCI evaluations to be combined with more qualitative measures.

The expected outcome of this evaluation is:

- a) To determine how intuitive the interface is to use
- b) To explore how the differences between how musicians and non-musicians interact with the interfaces
- c) To gather direct feedback from users about the usability of the interfaces

The user tests were performed as observed experiments where users were given versions of the interfaces on a laptop, and notes were taken as they used the interface. The experiment was split into two parts, whereby the first part consisted of the user practically using the interfaces, while the second consisted of free form interviews, where the participants were encouraged to share their views about the interfaces. The practical part of the experiment was itself split into smaller sections, the first of which was an observed free play session, in which participants were given three minutes to use each interface, without any explanation or outside influence. Each participant was told that they were to be presented with an interface for improvising with jazz music, and were shown how to operate the laptop, but nothing more. Different participants were shown both interfaces in a different order each time, in order to remove any effect knowledge of one interface may have on first impressions of the second, and notes were taken while the user explores the interface. Once the three minutes of each free play session was complete, the participant was then asked to explain how they believed the interface to work in order to gauge how much they had been able to work out about the interface, without instruction, as well as their level of engagement with the different aspects of each interface. Once participants had finished giving their explanations of the function of each interface, it is explained to them in detail how each one works, and a demonstration is given to clearly show them how to use the interface. They are then given one minute of observed exploration, in which notes are taken as they use the interface for the first time with instruction.

Following on from this, participants are told they will be presented with an example melody, which they will then be asked to attempt to reproduce using both of the interfaces. They are told they can listen to the example as many times as they wish, and they are given a short period of practice with the interface before the observation begins. Once users have completed this task, this represents the end of the practical part of the experiment. Users are then asked relatively freeform questions about their experiences with the interfaces, encouraging users to explain if they have a preference between the two interfaces and why, and explain their relationship with the output of the two interfaces. Users are also encouraged to share additional thoughts on the interfaces, which are all noted down during the experiment.

4.2.2 Results

In total 5 participants took part in the experiment, with their ages ranging from 26 to 66 comprising of 5 men and one woman. Three participants identified themselves as musicians, and two of those further identified themselves as actively performing musicians, while the other two participants stated that they did not consider themselves musicians.

4.2.2.1 Intervallic Keyboard Interface

When first presented with the Intervallic Keyboard interface for the 3-minute exploration session, all users were able to induce sound from the interface by clicking the buttons within the first minute. One user, who did not identify themselves to be a musician, first attempted to click on the keyboard visualisation, which they later explained was due to the familiarity of a keyboard, despite the fact this is relatively small on the interface. In general, the participants experimented with the interface, in an attempt to discover the limits of the interface, and to see what interactions it afforded. Two of the five participants began by pressing each button once on the interface, most participants then attempted pressing one of the buttons multiple times, moving up and down in the y axis in the process. Two of the participants that had identified themselves as musicians attempted to perform vibrato like motions on the keys. Both non-musical participants took the pitch of the instrument to an extreme, either to in-audible low notes or very high pitch high notes, which suggests the need for a mechanism to stop the pitch from becoming too low or too high. In general, the quality of melodic output from these sessions was poor, which the participants recognised themselves when asked at the end of their exploration session, with melodies relatively sporadic and participants more focussed on the function of the interface than the musical output.

When asked how they thought the interface worked, four of the five participants correctly stated that the pitch went up when clicking on the right-hand side of the interface, and went down when clicking on the left-hand side of the interface. The remaining participant could not provide a general explanation of how the interface worked. When asked specifically what happened when the centre button was pressed, none of the participants were able to answer correctly.

When asked to reproduce the example melody, almost all participants were unable to reproduce a melody that resembled the original in most forms. The participants that had declared themselves as non-musicians appeared to disregard any rhythmic aspects of the melody almost

immediately, and focussed on trying to reproduce the pitch content, and often appeared to be watching the colour visualisations, and trying to follow green notes. Those who identified as musicians appeared more frustrated, and often appeared to be looking for the right note, rather than just playing a melody. They would often move up and down in search of a particular note, before moving on to another part of the example melody.

4.2.2.2 Contour Interface

After being presented with the Contour interface, all participants very quickly (in less than 15 seconds) discovered that you could press anywhere on the screen to stop and start the sound from the instrument. Four of the five participants discovered within one minute that you could drag a note to begin a contour a change a not this way, and one participant never tried to drag. All of the participants that had identified as musicians attempted some sort of vibrato movement when dragging the contour. In general, the melodic output was of a higher quality than that from the Intervallic Keyboard interface, as participants attempted to draw contours, and seemed to care more about their rhythmic contributions, given that they didn't have to click to realise every single note, as with the other interface. One user, that had identified as a non-musician, experimented by clicking systematically along both the x and y axis, and later explained that they thought that clicking along the y axis had an effect on the sonic qualities of the note, however as this isn't the case, these sorts of conclusions should be treated as artefacts of this method of allowing for free experimentation.

When asked to explain their understanding of the interface, all of the participants correctly identified that movement in the y axis was mapped to differences in pitch, and the four participants that had performed dragged gestures during the experimentation mentioned that you could drag to draw melodies onto the screen. As previously mentioned, one participant incorrectly asserted that movement on the x-axis changed the sonic quality of the note being played.

Participants responses when asked to reproduce the example melody were largely similar to those with the previous interface, with, as expected, all participants unable to reproduce the melody effectively. As with this interface it is easier to move between notes quickly, it appeared that for those who identified as musicians, they were slightly less frustrated as they could quickly skip over a note if it wasn't as they expected, rather than have to find the correct button as with the previous interface.

When asked which interface they preferred, users were split between the two interfaces, with 3 preferring the Contour interface, and two the Intervallic Keyboard interface. There was no clear split between musicians and non-musicians, as Figure 18 demonstrates.

	Intervallic Keyboard Model	Contour Interface
Identified Musicians	1	2
Identified Non-musician	1	1

Figure 18: Participants declared preferred interface

When asked in particular what was important when considering which interface they preferred, participants listed a number of different reasons, including ease of use, enjoyability and functionality. One participant stated they could see themselves becoming more proficient with the Contour interface over the other, and listed this as their reason for a preference.

4.2.2.3 Summary

According to the aims of the project, the system aims to be an *“Instantly Knowable, Indefinitely Masterable Interface”*, following Golan Levin’s quote. Given that all users found the major functions of both interfaces within minutes, without instruction, implies that the interfaces certainly contain aspects that can be described as “instantly knowable”, allowing for a slight stretching of the term “instantly”. All of the participants said that they felt with more time, their skill with both interfaces would have improved, giving implication that the interface is more Masterable, however further evaluation with multiple sessions with each participant would be needed to measure whether users could reach a limit of ability with the interface.

The evaluation brought to light a number of small issues that impeded the use of the interface for some participants. The tendency of some of the participants that had identified as non-musicians to take the pitch to inaudible extremes, for example, highlighted the necessity for features such as a limit for pitch which would constrain the pitch within an acceptable range. As this wasn’t an issue for the participants who had identified as musicians, it’s clear this isn’t required for all users, but it’s something that should be taken into consideration for users who wouldn’t understand that low notes may become inaudible. In addition to this, it appeared that some of the participants, particularly those who had stated they active performing musicians, were searching for additional expressive actions which were not available – for example moving in a vibrato like motion to add vibrato. Adding expressivity effects to notes such as vibrato and legato modes would add greater power of creativity to the instrument, which would particularly affect those familiar with existing instruments that allow for vibrato and legato interactions.

In addition to this, it appeared that the most experienced musicians of the participants in particular felt quite frustrated with the instrument. However, this is to be expected as the instrument does not pertain to give full control to the performer, so any frustration experienced by more experienced users is understandable but expected. Particularly with the Intervallic Keyboard interface, it appeared that extensive familiarity with a traditional keyboard sometimes hindered participants understanding of the instrument, as it challenged some quite fundamental concepts about keyboards they had already attained. This was expected, given that the interface relies

heavily on this familiarity to be intuitive, but is inconsistent with users' expectations of a normal keyboard in a number of ways. It is fair to assume that while this may increase the learning period somewhat, with sufficient time, these users would be able to learn to deal with the less direct relationship with pitch that this interface allows.

5 Conclusion & Further Work

This project has contributed a novel approach to melody generation that utilises an adaptive use of variable-order Markov chains that takes harmonic context into account in order to produce high quality and stylistically consistent jazz melodies. In addition to this, the project has contributed two novel interfaces for improvising jazz melodies in real time, using suggestions from the melody generator, that allow for intuitive interaction on a touch screen device, and utilise interface metaphors that improve the use of the affordances of touch screen devices.

User testing has demonstrated that both interfaces are intuitive to use, as all test subjects were able to discover the main functions of the interfaces without any instruction, and were able to create melodies unaided. While melodic output in user test sessions was perceived poorly by participants, both computational and subjective, human based melody evaluations have shown that the melody generator is capable of producing melodies that are similar to those of authentic jazz melodies from standards. Additionally, all user participants declared that they felt they could improve their proficiency with further sessions, which shows the interface are in the right direction to fulfil the project aim of creating an interface that is *"Instantly Knowable, Indefinitely Masterable Interface"*.

From user testing it came to light that there were additional aspects of study that could be pursued in order to further meet the aims of the project. For example, during user experiments it became clear that there are a number of small alterations that could be made to the interfaces in order to improve their usability; namely the implementation of expressive parameters such as the ability to apply vibrato to notes as well as perform legato phrases, as well as to imposing a constraint on extreme high and low notes to keep melodies within an acceptable range. These are changes that would not take excessive time to implement, and would improve the interface for future use. Also, as is stated in the methodology, the interfaces currently only work on desktop computers as a proof of concept, and consequently all evaluation was performed on desktop computers. Thus, an obvious element of future work would be to migrate the interface to function on a touch screen device, and perform evaluations in this manner, user tests are likely to be different. As mentioned previously, all of the participants stated that they felt they needed more time with the interface to improve their ability and performance with it. This would suggest that further, recurring user experiments; whereby the same users would come back to be observed while using the interfaces; could prove fruitful, as it would provide further insight in users' learning curves while using the instrument. Without time consuming experiments and regular commitment from test subjects, it is difficult to determine when users reach a limit in terms of how much they can improve on the instrument, and how their learning of the instrument can be supported.

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7 Apendices

A. Melody Generation, Sound Engine and Interface Code Repository

<https://github.com/joemunday/upf-thesis>

B. Complete Melody Survey (see next page)

Melody Survey

*Required

1. Email address *

Welcome!

Thanks for participating in my melody survey. You'll be presented with a few samples of melodies, and asked a few short questions about each. There are two sections of the survey, and it shouldn't take more than 10 minutes to complete.

Below is an example melody like the ones you will be presented with in the survey, which consists of a melody and an accompaniment. Please play it and check that you can clearly hear the melody, and adjust your volume to your preference. Please note that headphones are recommended.

The three questions concern the following aspects of the melody:

- 1). How much you like the melody
- 2). How jazzy you think the melody is
- 3.) How natural you think the melody is

For each, you're asked to provide a value between 1 and 10. This is a survey of personal opinion and there are no wrong answers, so please be honest about your ratings!

Example Melody

[v=rGASyUH8Hel](http://youtube.com/watch?v=rGASyUH8Hel)

<http://youtube.com/watch?>

2. How much do you like this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
I strongly dislike it	<input type="radio"/>	I like it a lot									

3. How jazzy was this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all jazzy	<input type="radio"/>	Very jazzy									

4. How natural was this melody?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all natural	<input type="radio"/>	Very natural									

Melody 1

Melody 1

<http://youtube.com/watch?v=ALHWZ7hby3E>

[v=ALHWZ7hby3E](http://youtube.com/watch?v=ALHWZ7hby3E)

5. How much do you like this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
I strongly dislike it	<input type="radio"/>	I like it a lot									

6. How jazzy was this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all jazzy	<input type="radio"/>	Very jazzy									

7. How natural was this melody?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all natural	<input type="radio"/>	Very natural									

Melody 2

Melody 2

<http://youtube.com/watch?v=ygJUbfzWcdw>

[v=ygJUbfzWcdw](http://youtube.com/watch?v=ygJUbfzWcdw)

8. How much do you like this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
I strongly dislike it	<input type="radio"/>	I like it a lot									

9. How jazzy was this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all jazzy	<input type="radio"/>	Very jazzy									

10. How natural was this melody?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all natural	<input type="radio"/>	Very natural									

Melody 3

Melody 3

<http://youtube.com/watch?v=vX7BcvcPY8I>

11. How much do you like this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
I strongly dislike it	<input type="radio"/>	I like it a lot									

12. How jazzy was this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all jazzy	<input type="radio"/>	Very jazzy									

13. How natural was this melody?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all natural	<input type="radio"/>	Very natural									

Melody 4

Melody 4

<http://youtube.com/watch?v=gQwrFxpUxM>

14. How much do you like this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
I strongly dislike it	<input type="radio"/>	I like it a lot									

15. **How jazzy was this melody? ***

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all jazzy	<input type="radio"/>	Very jazzy									

16. **How natural was this melody?**

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all natural	<input type="radio"/>	Very natural									

Melody 5

Melody 5

<http://youtube.com/watch?v=Qel4cCO8xp0>

17. **How much do you like this melody? ***

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
I strongly dislike it	<input type="radio"/>	I like it a lot									

18. **How jazzy was this melody? ***

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all jazzy	<input type="radio"/>	Very jazzy									

19. **How natural was this melody?**

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all natural	<input type="radio"/>	Very natural									

Melody 6

Melody 6

http://youtube.com/watch?v=x-pseUOI-_E

20. **How much do you like this melody? ***

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
I strongly dislike it	<input type="radio"/>	I like it a lot									

21. How jazzy was this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all jazzy	<input type="radio"/>	Very jazzy									

22. How natural was this melody?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all natural	<input type="radio"/>	Very natural									

Melody 7

Melody 7

[http://youtube.com/watch?](http://youtube.com/watch?v=MidfhZwYMQw)

[v=MidfhZwYMQw](http://youtube.com/watch?v=MidfhZwYMQw)

23. How much do you like this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
I strongly dislike it	<input type="radio"/>	I like it a lot									

24. **How jazzy was this melody? ***

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all jazzy	<input type="radio"/>	Very jazzy									

25. **How natural was this melody?**

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all natural	<input type="radio"/>	Very natural									

Melody 8

Melody 8

<http://youtube.com/watch?v=KjOiKFKIxMY>

26. **How much do you like this melody? ***

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
I strongly dislike it	<input type="radio"/>	I like it a lot									

27. How jazzy was this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all jazzy	<input type="radio"/>	Very jazzy									

28. How natural was this melody?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all natural	<input type="radio"/>	Very natural									

Melody 9

Melody 9

<http://youtube.com/watch?v=X1iwfgdkqBQ>

29. How much do you like this melody? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
I strongly dislike it	<input type="radio"/>	I like it a lot									

30. **How jazzy was this melody? ***

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all jazzy	<input type="radio"/>	Very jazzy									

31. **How natural was this melody?**

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all natural	<input type="radio"/>	Very natural									

Melody 10

Melody 10

<http://youtube.com/watch?v=bl-sWLkiOIU>

32. **How much do you like this melody? ***

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
I strongly dislike it	<input type="radio"/>	I like it a lot									

33. **How jazzy was this melody? ****Mark only one oval.*

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all jazzy	<input type="radio"/>	Very jazzy									

34. **How natural was this melody?***Mark only one oval.*

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all natural	<input type="radio"/>	Very natural									

Part 2

For this part you will be played more samples of melodies, and this time asked if you remember them from the previous section.

Please listen to the melody sample, and answer the question below each sample.

Melody 11**Melody 11**

<http://youtube.com/watch?v=8x1ueCNWm6s>

35. **Do you remember this melody?***Mark only one oval.*

- I don't remember this melody at all
- I somewhat remember this melody
- I definitely remember this melody

Melody 12

Melody 12

http://youtube.com/watch?v=dYOCWI_h8bE

36. **Do you remember this melody?**

Mark only one oval.

- I don't remember this melody at all
- I somewhat remember this melody
- I definitely remember this melody

Melody 13

Melody 13

<http://youtube.com/watch?v=yi1cCbmEYfU>

37. **Do you remember this melody?**

Mark only one oval.

- I don't remember this melody at all
- I somewhat remember this melody
- I definitely remember this melody

Melody 14

Melody 14

[http://youtube.com/watch?](http://youtube.com/watch?v=2JH8TkLqv0w)

[v=2JH8TkLqv0w](http://youtube.com/watch?v=2JH8TkLqv0w)

38. **Do you remember this melody?**

Mark only one oval.

- I don't remember this melody at all
- I somewhat remember this melody
- I definitely remember this melody

Melody 15

Melody 15

[http://youtube.com/watch?](http://youtube.com/watch?v=FQMFjlvbNLk)

[v=FQMFjlvbNLk](http://youtube.com/watch?v=FQMFjlvbNLk)

39. **Do you remember this melody?**

Mark only one oval.

- I don't remember this melody at all
- I somewhat remember this melody
- I definitely remember this melody

Melody 16

Melody 16

[http://youtube.com/watch?](http://youtube.com/watch?v=pKT8CFBm76o)

[v=pKT8CFBm76o](http://youtube.com/watch?v=pKT8CFBm76o)

40. **Do you remember this melody?**

Mark only one oval.

- I don't remember this melody at all
- I somewhat remember this melody
- I definitely remember this melody

Melody 17

Melody 17

[http://youtube.com/watch?](http://youtube.com/watch?v=VANgLXTWiUs)

[v=VANgLXTWiUs](http://youtube.com/watch?v=VANgLXTWiUs)

41. **Do you remember this melody?**

Mark only one oval.

- I don't remember this melody at all
- I somewhat remember this melody
- I definitely remember this melody

Melody 18

Melody 18

[http://youtube.com/watch?](http://youtube.com/watch?v=I9nkHRSzb9o)

[v=I9nkHRSzb9o](http://youtube.com/watch?v=I9nkHRSzb9o)

42. Do you remember this melody?

Mark only one oval.

- I don't remember this melody at all
- I somewhat remember this melody
- I definitely remember this melody

Melody 19

Melody 19

[http://youtube.com/watch?](http://youtube.com/watch?v=vu0hMt_cS8U)

[v=vu0hMt_cS8U](http://youtube.com/watch?v=vu0hMt_cS8U)

43. Do you remember this melody?

Mark only one oval.

- I don't remember this melody at all
- I somewhat remember this melody
- I definitely remember this melody

Your Information

Thanks for taking part in the survey.

Please answer a few short questions about yourself to complete the form.

44. **Age:**

45. **Gender:**

Mark only one oval.

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

46. **Did you recognise any of the musical pieces from the extracts? If so and you can remember their titles, please list their names below:**

Mark only one oval.

- I didn't recognise any of the pieces
- I did recognise one or more of the pieces, but can't remember their titles
- Other: _____

47. **Which of the following musical genres do you listen to regularly?**

Tick all that apply.

- Pop
- Rock
- Jazz
- Classical
- Hip-Hop
- Electronic Dance Music
- Blues
- Reggae
- Other: _____

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C. Melody Evaluation Survey Results

Question Number	1	1	1	2	2	2
Participant	Rating	Jazziness	Naturalness	Rating	Jazziness	Naturalness
1	8	7	5	6	8	3
2	5	1	3	6	8	7
3	9	7	8	8	6	6
4	4	1	4	8	3	7
5	6	10	3	5	1	3
6	5	7	4	8	2	8
7	6	1	6	3	1	7
8	9	6	4	5	9	3
9	6	1	5	3	8	3
10	6	2	2	8	4	5
11	4	10	3	8	2	6
12	6	5	2	4	8	5
13	7	10	3	6	5	4
14	7	5	4	8	5	5
15	10	1	3	3	4	4
16	8	6	5	4	5	7
17	10	6	8	7	10	7
18	4	2	5	6	10	4
19	5	5	4	7	6	5

Question Number	3	3	3	4	4	4
Participant	Rating	Jazziness	Naturalness	Rating	Jazziness	Naturalness
1	5	4	2	2	4	1
2	3	4	3	1	10	2
3	3	1	5	3	10	5
4	5	9	4	2	8	1
5	4	10	8	1	4	3
6	4	7	6	3	1	3
7	5	1	3	2	8	3
8	3	8	3	3	3	1
9	4	9	4	2	5	1
10	3	9	8	3	5	2
11	6	6	8	1	3	1
12	3	9	3	1	7	1
13	6	9	4	2	2	1
14	5	10	6	1	8	3
15	6	10	6	2	1	1
16	5	10	5	2	7	3
17	8	6	4	1	9	1
18	7	7	3	1	10	6
19	5	1	6	3	9	2

Question Number	5	5	5	6	6	6
Participant	Rating	Jazziness	Naturalness	Rating	Jazziness	Naturalness
1	3	5	2	8	6	10
2	2	1	3	8	6	10
3	4	9	6	7	10	8
4	1	2	2	7	9	6
5	2	4	2	8	6	9
6	2	4	3	7	8	10
7	2	4	3	8	9	7
8	3	4	2	6	6	7
9	1	8	3	10	5	8
10	4	8	1	6	8	6
11	3	5	1	9	4	10
12	3	8	3	7	6	6
13	2	2	1	9	8	10
14	2	6	1	8	9	6
15	4	3	2	10	4	7
16	1	10	1	6	6	8
17	3	10	1	9	10	7
18	3	3	5	8	5	8
19	1	4	2	9	8	8

Question Number	7	7	7	8	8	8
Participant	Rating	Rating	Jazziness	Naturalness	Rating	Jazziness
1	8	9	8	10	9	8
2	6	8	9	9	7	2
3	9	9	10	9	9	8
4	9	4	10	6	8	9
5	10	8	9	4	8	6
6	8	6	8	7	2	8
7	10	9	6	8	8	9
8	10	6	8	8	9	2
9	10	4	8	8	8	7
10	10	7	6	3	1	10
11	8	4	9	6	10	9
12	7	8	8	7	6	8
13	6	5	9	4	1	6
14	8	4	9	9	10	6
15	7	10	7	3	4	7
16	8	5	6	9	8	8
17	10	5	8	9	2	5
18	7	9	8	4	10	6
19	6	5	9	8	7	6

Question Number	9	9	9	10	10	10
Participant	Naturalness	Rating	Jazziness	Naturalness	Rating	Jazziness
1	7	6	4	7	4	4
2	7	1	8	7	4	3
3	3	1	7	4	7	4
4	7	9	6	4	6	5
5	2	6	7	4	7	3
6	7	10	3	6	1	3
7	8	8	7	10	10	7
8	3	1	4	8	8	3
9	6	7	7	7	6	4
10	3	5	5	9	3	7
11	2	1	3	6	7	3
12	5	8	5	6	2	8
13	6	7	4	8	5	2
14	5	3	3	7	8	3
15	4	10	8	10	8	4
16	8	10	3	8	8	4
17	7	8	8	5	1	3
18	6	4	3	6	9	2
19	4	7	3	6	4	4

Question
Number

11

12

Participant	Do you remember this melody?	Do you remember this melody?
1	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody
2	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
3	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody
4	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
5	I definitely remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
6	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
7	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
8	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody
9	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
10	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
11	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
12	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
13	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
14	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
15	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody
16	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
17	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
18	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
19	I definitely remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody

Question
Number

13

14

Participant	Do you remember this melody?	Do you remember this melody?
1	I definitely remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
2	I somewhat remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody
3	I definitely remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody
4	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
5	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
6	I definitely remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
7	I definitely remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody
8	I definitely remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
9	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
10	I definitely remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
11	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
12	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
13	I definitely remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
14	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody
15	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
16	I definitely remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
17	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody
18	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
19	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody

Question
Number

15

16

Participant	Do you remember this melody?	Do you remember this melody?
1	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
2	I definitely remember this melody	I definitely remember this melody
3	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
4	I definitely remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
5	I don't remember this melody at all	I definitely remember this melody
6	I somewhat remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody
7	I somewhat remember this melody	I definitely remember this melody
8	I definitely remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody
9	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
10	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
11	I somewhat remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody
12	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
13	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
14	I definitely remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody
15	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
16	I somewhat remember this melody	I definitely remember this melody
17	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
18	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
19	I somewhat remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody

Question
Number

17

18

Participant	Do you remember this melody?	Do you remember this melody?
1	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody
2	I somewhat remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody
3	I definitely remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
4	I don't remember this melody at all	I definitely remember this melody
5	I somewhat remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody
6	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody
7	I don't remember this melody at all	I definitely remember this melody
8	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody
9	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
10	I somewhat remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody
11	I somewhat remember this melody	I somewhat remember this melody
12	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody
13	I don't remember this melody at all	I definitely remember this melody
14	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
15	I somewhat remember this melody	I don't remember this melody at all
16	I don't remember this melody at all	I somewhat remember this melody
17	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
18	I don't remember this melody at all	I don't remember this melody at all
19	I somewhat remember this melody	I definitely remember this melody

Participant	Do you remember this melody?
1	I somewhat remember this melody
2	I don't remember this melody at all
3	I somewhat remember this melody
4	I definitely remember this melody
5	I somewhat remember this melody
6	I don't remember this melody at all
7	I somewhat remember this melody
8	I definitely remember this melody
9	I somewhat remember this melody
10	I don't remember this melody at all
11	I somewhat remember this melody
12	I somewhat remember this melody
13	I definitely remember this melody
14	I somewhat remember this melody
15	I don't remember this melody at all
16	I somewhat remember this melody
17	I somewhat remember this melody
18	I don't remember this melody at all
19	I don't remember this melody at all